

THE USE OF CLASP DENTURES IN THE CLINIC OF ORTHOPEDIC DENTISTRY**Kuzieva Madina Abdusalimovna**

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Abstract. *The problem of dentistry in the development and creation of new dental prosthetics systems that would contribute to improving the quality of life and reducing the rehabilitation period of dental patients, at the present time, remains very relevant. Clasp prosthetics is a fairly progressive type of this field, which has a number of advantages, but also a number of disadvantages, in which this type of orthopedic treatment is not suitable in all cases of patient prosthetics.*

Keywords: *clasp denture, clasp dentures, clasp fastening.*

ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ БЮГЕЛЬНЫХ ПРОТЕЗОВ В КЛИНИКЕ ОРТОПЕДИЧЕСКОЙ СТОМАТОЛОГИИ

Аннотация. *Проблема стоматологии в разработке и создании новых систем зубного протезирования, которые бы способствовали улучшению качества жизни и сокращению сроков реабилитации стоматологических больных, в настоящее время остается весьма актуальной. Бюгельное протезирование является достаточно прогрессивным видом данного направления, имеющим ряд преимуществ, но и ряд недостатков, при которых данный вид ортопедического лечения подходит не во всех случаях протезирования пациентов.*

Ключевые слова: *бюгельный протез, бюгельные протезы, кламмерное крепление.*

Clasp prosthetics is one of the types of removable dental prosthetics, which is currently the most convenient and advanced among the proposed types of dental prosthetics. This type of prosthesis is an arched cast metal frame, which is covered with an acrylic plastic base and artificial teeth are installed on it. It is fixed in the oral cavity using hooks-clasps, which very tightly cover the supporting tooth. Since the prosthesis has an arched metal structure, this allows you to effectively distribute the load between the teeth and gums. When compared with other similar modifications from various plastic structures, this type of prosthesis allows you to refuse to thicken the plastic layer, reduces the weight and volume of the structure, and also maintains its strength and stability.

The clasp prosthesis has a number of indications for its use:

- 1) 1, 2, 3 class according to Kennedy,
- 2) if it is necessary to correct a dental anomaly, such as malocclusion,
- 3) when splinting,
- 4) in case of periodontosis of I and II degrees, the design of the clasp denture must be special – all natural teeth are included in the denture, they perform a retaining and supporting function,
- 5) in case of deep or decreasing bite, it is advisable to increase it with a continuous clasp located on the front upper teeth,
- 6) removal of a large number of teeth (immediate prosthesis),
- 7) absence of even one tooth (aesthetic prosthesis),
- 8) large-scale traumatic treatment of teeth carried out for the proposed bridge prostheses,
- 9) the serious condition of patients requiring prostheses,

- 10) refusal of patients to use fixed prosthetics,
- 11) replacement of an old, functionally incompetent prosthesis with a new one,
- 12) in case of galvanosis, allergic reactions of the body to metal prostheses.

This type of removable denture allows fixation both on natural living teeth and on already installed or destroyed teeth or crowns. If the design of the clasp denture is chosen correctly, its fastenings will perform a reinforcing function for the teeth on which it is supported, and it is possible to extend their service life. The installation of a clasp denture is determined not so much by the number of teeth on the jaw, but by their strength, as well as the condition of the gums and oral cavity in general. So in some cases, this prosthesis can be installed even with a minimum number of teeth.

Types of clasp dentures.

Clasp dentures have different fixation on the remaining teeth in the oral cavity. They can be on clasps, on locks and on telescopic crowns. Different systems of fixation of dentures have both advantages and disadvantages.

Clasp-type partial dentures.

This design is fixed with the help of hooks-clasps, which very tightly embrace the supporting tooth. Clasps are made of metal. With their help, the prosthesis is firmly held on the jaw and transfers the load to the teeth when chewing. Clasps are most often cast together with the frame, so this design is very strong and durable. Clasps are selected individually, based on the size and shape of the teeth.

Clasp clasp dentures are the best option for dental prosthetics, which have only one drawback - low aesthetics. When smiling, metal hooks may be visible in the mouth. However, this only applies to individual cases when installing a denture in another way is simply clinically impossible.

It is also worth noting the higher cost of this type of dentures compared to plastic analogues. But this difference is fully justified by the fact that clasp dentures have a more complex manufacturing technology.

Clasp dentures with a locking system.

This type of clasp dentures does not have metal hooks, so its appearance is more aesthetic.

Clasp dentures on locks have a strong lightweight bridge structure, which during chewing transfers part of the pressure to the supporting teeth. To protect and strengthen the supporting teeth, they are preliminarily covered with metal-ceramic crowns, where half of the lock is inserted, and the other half is located on the supporting teeth. Locks fixed in the teeth or in the crowns of the teeth provide high strength of the denture fastening. In addition, they allow you to securely fix the structure and easily remove it for periodic cleaning. But they also have a number of disadvantages.

One of them is the complexity of manufacture. Currently, this is the most high-tech design in dental prosthetics, the manufacture of which requires highly qualified dental technicians and orthopedists. In the manufacture of such a prosthesis, high accuracy of calculation of all elements of the structure is important. This leads to the second disadvantage - high cost. And the third disadvantage is the participation of a large number of teeth in the structure. This type of clasp prosthesis requires mandatory protection of the supporting teeth with metal-ceramic crowns, since the locking fasteners are located on them.

Clasp denture on telescopic crowns is already considered the most aesthetic design of this type. A retractable (telescopic) crown serves for fixation: its removable part is attached to the base of the structure, and the non-removable part is fixed to the supporting teeth. To install such a prosthesis, it is necessary to grind the teeth, cover them with metal, polish them, and only then install the clasp. This type of prosthesis is very difficult to manufacture, since for its stability, the non-removable and removable parts of the crown must absolutely match. Also, the very high cost is a disadvantage of this type of prosthetics.

Advantages and disadvantages of clasp prosthetics.

Advantages:

1. The clasp denture is supported not only by the alveolar ridge, but also by the teeth, thus correctly distributing the load between them;
2. The clasp denture does not have a massive plastic base covering the palate; it is replaced by a metal arch;
3. Compactness, lightness and aesthetics of the clasp denture;
4. Long service life of the prosthesis.

Flaws:

1. Like all removable dentures, which include the clasp denture, it cannot be worn constantly without being removed;
2. If the clasp denture is fixed with clasps, the brackets of the fastenings may in some cases be visible when smiling;
3. As with any other type of prosthesis, one needs to get used to wearing a clasp denture, so at first patients have to experience some discomfort.

Special attention should be paid to the price of clasp prosthetics. The cost of installing clasp prostheses is formed from a number of factors. Before making and installing a clasp prosthesis, the dentist prepares the oral cavity (therapeutic, periodontal treatment). These works should be taken into account, otherwise the estimated price of prosthetics may in reality be significantly higher than what the patient initially assumed. It should also be taken into account that the price of a clasp prosthesis will depend on the type of fixation of the prosthesis to the teeth. Clasp prosthetics on locks is much more expensive, since in this case the total cost also includes the cost of locks and metal-ceramic crowns.

Conclusions.

Most experts and specialists in the field of dentistry believe that at present there is no alternative to clasp dentures. Currently, clasp dentures cope with their main tasks at the proper level - the restoration of lost chewing functions and the creation of a cosmetic effect of healthy teeth. The only significant disadvantage of this type of prosthetics is the cost of clasp dentures, since not every patient can afford to use this type of service in orthopedic treatment.

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